

Should the climate movement organise around extreme weather events?

Discussion paper

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About the series

This is the first in a series of discussion papers exploring where the climate movement might focus its energy and resources. Each paper examines a different frontier for climate organising - taking on the insurance industry, calling for taxes on the super rich, making polluters pay, or building alliances with the AI safety movement. We're developing these papers in collaboration with thinkers and strategists from across the movement. Our goal is to spark debate, share evidence from recent campaigns, and help organisers make choices about where to invest limited movement resources. We're open to suggestions - if you see other promising frontiers we should explore, [get in touch](#). This first paper, co-authored with Maciej Muskat from Greenpeace International, examines an important and often neglected area: activism around extreme weather events.

Summary

Extreme weather events are creating a new generation of climate activists - people whose homes have flooded, whose communities have been destroyed by storms, and for whom climate change is not an abstract threat. This discussion paper examines whether the climate movement should organise more systematically around these moments of crisis. Drawing on case studies from Vermont, the Philippines, and Spain, we identify common elements of successful campaigns: acting fast while public attention is high, centring affected communities rather than professional activists, using attribution science to connect disasters to specific corporate actors, building coalitions beyond traditional environmentalists, and making concrete demands for accountability. We argue that extreme weather events offer a strategic opportunity to expand the movement's base and win tangible policy victories - but only if organisers are prepared to act with sensitivity and speed when disasters strike.

Keywords: extreme weather events, climate attribution, climate activism, social movements, fossil fuel accountability, climate litigation, climate superfund, disaster organising, climate policy, corporate responsibility

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Cover image: Debris lines the streets of Tacloban, Leyte island, following Typhoon Haiyan, November 14, 2013. Photo: [Trocaire](#) from Ireland. Licensed under [CC Attribution 2.0 Generic license](#), via Wikimedia Commons.

Introduction

As Nicolo Wojewoda [wrote](#) in 2023, Europe's climate movement feels 'fractured and stuck'. The 2018/19 years of hope seem a distant memory. State repression has intensified. Omnicrises abound. Authoritarianism and populism are on the rise, While public support for climate action remains strong, [the public consistently underestimate how much others care](#) - giving people the sense that they are unusual in worrying and perhaps hindering active participation. The movement is currently neither large enough, diverse enough, nor loud enough to have significant impact.

Groups like Just Stop Oil, Letzte Generation and Climate Defiance deserve credit for having kept the climate in the headlines when many would rather ignore it. Campaigners' stream of disruptive actions has maintained attention and pressure when institutional channels have lost credibility and fallen from the news - who even pays attention to COP these days? But any movement whose only visible face is civil disobedience will struggle to expand beyond its core. It leaves itself open to being portrayed as extreme and out of touch, making it easier for politicians to dismiss.

So what tools does the movement have that could create renewed momentum of the sort we saw in 2018/19?

Every day, [extreme weather events](#) (EWE) are gestating a new wave of climate activists, many of whom have never attended a protest nor read a climate report. These are people whose homes have flooded, or whose communities have been destroyed by storms or wildfires. For them, climate change is not some abstract future scenario. Their houses are quite literally [on fire](#). These are real communities - people from across the political spectrum - facing immediate crisis and they are in the headlines with increasing regularity. From these tragedies, sensitive though it is, there is a window of possibility for political change.

Counting the cost

The numbers are stark. Between 2000 and 2019, floods alone affected [over 1.65 billion people globally](#), killing more than 100,000. The rise in global temperatures made last year's Valencia floods [twice as likely](#) and 12% more intense. Super Typhoon Odette in the Philippines caused [₱47.8 billion](#) (£685 million) in damages. Vermont's 2023 flooding resulted in [\\$1 billion](#) in damage claims.

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For climate organisers, these events do something that years of climate advocacy often can't: they make the connection between fossil fuels and their real harms immediate and visceral. [Recent research](#) published in Nature found that while exposure to extreme weather alone doesn't automatically increase support for climate policy, "subjective attribution does" - that is, when people understand that a specific disaster was worsened by climate change and can connect it to specific corporate actors, their opinion shifts. That's when, with sensitivity, empathy, and the power of firsthand experience, organisers can make headway.

[Climate attribution](#) science has become sophisticated enough to quantify how much a company's emissions contributed to making a specific storm deadlier or a heatwave more intense. [The methodology](#) is based on comparing two worlds: the one we live in versus a counterfactual world without human-caused warming. Researchers use climate models to simulate many versions of both scenarios, generating large numbers of possible weather outcomes. By comparing the probability distributions of extreme events between these two worlds, they can estimate how much more (or less) likely an event became due to climate change, or how much more intense it was.

Shell, for instance, is [historically responsible for 41 billion tonnes of CO2](#) or more than 2% of global fossil fuel emissions - a tangible indicator of the level of Shell's responsibility for the effect of that environmental pollution. This isn't abstract anymore. It's evidence that can be used in courtrooms, legislative hearings and public campaigns.

There's also a powerful economic pressure point that campaigners are learning to exploit. The insurance industry is caught in an unsustainable contradiction: climate disasters are already costing insurers dearly (roughly [\\$600 billion in climate related losses](#) from 2002 to 2022), yet many insurers continue to underwrite new fossil fuel projects. For 28 major insurers analysed in 2023, [climate disaster losses almost equalled the premiums](#) they earned from insuring fossil fuel clients. When disasters strike, this contradiction becomes politically untenable. Communities devastated by floods or fires whilst their insurers back new oil projects makes for a sickeningly compelling campaign narrative. [The current EWE costs in 2025 alone in the EU are conservatively calculated at 43-50bn Euro](#), which is just slightly below the EU Commission's biggest budget item - the Common Agricultural Policy programme. The magnitude of the challenge is clear.

Winning in the time of extreme weather events - 3 case studies

We have looked at three places where communities organised around extreme weather and won concrete victories - not just raising awareness or getting media traction, but tangible wins on policy change and corporate accountability.

Vermont: bipartisan coalition after consecutive floods

Vermont National Guard helicopter surveys flood damage in Montpelier, Vermont, July 11, 2023. Photo by Air Force Senior Master Sgt. Michael Davis, U.S. Department of Defense. Public domain. Attribution: [The National Guard](#), [CC BY 2.0](#), via Wikimedia Commons.

When Vermont experienced catastrophic flooding, causing over \$1 billion in damage, in July 2023, it came in the wake of Tropical Storm Irene which had once already devastated the state in the decade before. Two such major floods galvanised an unusual coalition.

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The organisers' strategy was pragmatic and non partisan. Environmental groups like Vermont Natural Resources Council and the Sierra Club joined forces with farmers whose fields had been destroyed and small business owners whose livelihoods were underwater. State Senator Dick Sears, a Democrat, framed the proposed Climate Superfund Act around a principle everyone could understand - that those responsible for damage should pay for it. "Vermont has been willing to take on huge multinational corporations before, including when we held Saint-Gobain accountable for contaminating people's drinking water. The Climate Superfund Act [says] *the polluter pays*."

The coalition deliberately crossed party lines. This is worth noting - EWEs might be that rare thing that can overcome the paralysing power of polarisation. And this kind of bipartisanship can change the political arithmetic. The bill passed the Vermont Senate 21-5 and became law in May 2024 - the first of its kind in the US. It requires fossil fuel companies that have produced more than 1 billion metric tons of CO2 equivalent, to pay their share of Vermont's climate damages, based on their contribution to global emissions.

What made this work? Organisers centred affected communities, used climate attribution science to make the connection between EWE and fossil fuels concrete, and framed it around an acceptable, common sense principle ('Polluters pay') rather than partisan climate politics. They also moved quickly - introducing legislation while memories of flooded homes were still fresh and people were still calculating reconstruction costs.

Philippines: innovative legal strategies and international solidarity

Aerial view of Tacloban city after Super Typhoon Haiyan. Photo: [Marcel Crozet / ILO](#), November 2013. Licensed under [CC BY-NC-ND 3.0 IGO](#)

When Super Typhoon Haiyan hit in 2013, killing over 6,000 people, survivors like Joanna Sustento - who lost both parents and most of her family - didn't just mourn, they organised. The disaster exposed deep failures in government response: aid arrived too slowly, reconstruction efforts stalled amid accusations of corruption and mismanagement, and billions in promised housing assistance never materialised. Protests erupted as survivors demanded accountability - not just for the immediate chaos, but for years of inadequate disaster preparedness in one of the world's most typhoon-prone countries.

This organised anger became the foundation for a new approach. In 2015, Haiyan survivors partnered with Greenpeace Philippines to petition the Commission on Human Rights to investigate 47 "carbon major" fossil fuel companies for human rights violations related to climate change. The petition emerged from survivors who had built real political power

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through their organising: they were channeling community rage into a strategy for long-term accountability. This launched the National Inquiry on Climate Change - the world's first investigation into corporate responsibility for climate impacts.

The inquiry held evidence sessions in Manila, London, and New York over three years, documenting testimonies from typhoon survivors and climate scientists. In 2022, the Commission released findings that fossil fuel companies could be held morally and legally responsible for climate-related human rights violations.

In July 2025, following severe flooding in Metro Manila, Greenpeace staged an action that called attention to the government's failure to protect communities. They showed that up to USD\$17 bn may have been lost to corruption. Public anger intensified, culminating in a wave of powerful, large-scale protests that forced corruption and climate accountability to the top of the political priority list. This changed the dynamic - the surge of public pressure gave the CLIMA Bill (legal frameworks for climate loss and damage, corporate accountability, and reparations) the momentum it needed to advance.

The decade of activism and organising is now entering a new phase. In October 2025, 67 survivors of Super Typhoon Odette (Rai) - which killed over 400 people in 2021 - filed the first civil lawsuit directly linking a fossil fuel company to deaths and personal injuries in the Global South. They're suing Shell in UK courts under Philippine law for damages, using climate attribution science showing that climate change more than doubled the likelihood of an extreme event like Odette.

This case shows that in the time of polycrisis, survivors and NGOs need to demonstrate their political power. It was only through this sustained public pressure, that the legal strategy had teeth. Crucially, organisers had built the foundations and organising infrastructure to act when the next disaster hit. They had the capacity to ratchet up public pressure when it was most needed.

Spain: from floods and fires to a National Climate Emergency Pact

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Volunteers cleaning up in Sedavi following the devastating DANA floods in Valencia, Spain. Photo: [Pacopac](#) 2 November 2024. Licensed under [CC Attribution-Share Alike 4.0 International license](#).

The Valencia floods of October 2024 killed 237 people and displaced thousands. Images of cars floating down European city streets better known for their bars and cafes shocked people all over the world. The immediate response was mass mobilisation - more than 130,000 people marched in Valencia demanding accountability from regional officials who had delayed emergency warnings. Protests, organised by over 200 Valencian social organisations, continued for months.

Organisers didn't stop at demanding resignations. They wanted certainty that the system would change. In August 2025, following both the Valencia floods and devastating ongoing summer wildfires, Prime Minister Pedro Sánchez announced a Climate Emergency Pact.

The pact includes concrete measures: a new State Agency for Civil Protection and Emergencies to coordinate disaster response; year-round maintenance of firefighting staff (previously only reinforced in summer) and mandatory corporate carbon reporting. Billions

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in funding for climate adaptation infrastructure, probably the key element of any future resilience, are still “potential” and will require more pressure from the bottom up.

What's notable here, as with the Vermont case, is how organisers used the disaster to build a broader coalition that transcended normal political divisions. Sánchez framed it as requiring participation from "all public administrations, parliamentary groups, civil society, science, business, trade unions, and the country as a whole."

What climate organisers can learn

These three examples share common elements that may be informative for climate movement organisers when responding to future crises:

1. Act fast. When EWEs strike, time is a crucial factor, as both the media and those skeptical about climate (whether deniers or delayers) move swiftly to stake the ground and influence the narrative. It's crucial to be prepared, to offer direct assistance (beyond the work being done by relief organisations) and to help local community campaigns broadcast their story and demands.

2. Centre the affected communities and give them agency. The most powerful voices weren't climate activists - they were farmers who lost crops, business owners whose storefronts flooded, parents who lost children, and the first responders - groups extremely well trusted by the general public. These voices cut across political and demographic lines in ways professional activists rarely can. And they reduce the risk of outside actors being seen as taking advantage of disasters. Climate activists must step back to let authentic, trusted local voices take centre stage. Giving impacted communities agency (not portraying them as ‘victims’ but as agents of change) makes communities stronger and more eager to engage politically.

3. Use attribution science strategically. Climate attribution research has become sophisticated enough to quantify corporate responsibility and it's getting better and faster every year. Vermont used it to calculate damages. The Philippines case relies on it to prove Shell's contribution. This transforms abstract climate change into concrete accountability.

4. Use stories as well as facts. In terms of mass reach, the stories of real people, particularly rapid responders and firefighters, are often the most effective at cutting through. If these people say that the frequency and size of EWEs is growing each year, people are likely to believe it.

5. Build coalitions beyond the 'usual suspects'. Vermont united environmentalists with Republican farmers. Spain brought together municipal leaders, unions, and businesses. The Philippines connected typhoon survivors across multiple disasters. None of these looked like typical climate coalitions.

6. Target specific actors and make concrete demands. Rather than vague calls for climate action, these campaigns identified specific villains (fossil fuel companies) and specific responses (climate superfund laws, corporate liability, emergency infrastructure). People can rally around clear targets and tangible goals.

The path forward

Years ago, we watched movies portraying events we are now witnessing on a weekly basis. We are in the era of consequences.

Extreme weather events will keep happening. They will affect more people and cause more catastrophic damage. They are moments of horrific crisis and clarity, when the ears of the world are more open. They will continue to create more potential organising moments. These are not without risk; initially in the Valencia case, it was the far right Vox party who were first to appear on the scene, using the space as a chance for scapegoating. The climate movement can't afford to be risk averse and must step in to seize the narrative.

Many in the news media know these are key moments to convey the seriousness of the climate crisis. One news editor [reportedly said](#), 'The major climate story of the year isn't COP, it's summer.' Extreme weather gets coverage in ways that UN negotiations never will. These are the stories that reach beyond the climate choir to the whole congregation - everyone whose insurance rates just spiked or whose neighbourhood was just evacuated.

The climate movement doesn't need to abandon other tactics. But it does need to expand its repertoire and its base. [It needs new ideas](#). That means having organisers ready to support affected communities. It means having legal strategies prepared. It means building relationships now with farmers' associations, growing business coalitions and listening to local leaders who will be the natural allies if disaster strikes their communities.

The most powerful climate organising might not look like climate organising at all. It might look like flood survivors demanding accountability and funding for measures to lower the impact of the next EWE, farmers seeking compensation for climate damages and support

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to regenerate and climate-proof their land, or parents fighting for their children's future after their town burned down.

These people aren't peripheral to the climate fight. They are the climate fight.

For climate organisers looking to learn more about extreme weather attribution and organising strategies, resources include the [World Weather Attribution](#) initiative, the [Climate Accountability Institute](#) and the [Center for Climate Integrity's](#) toolkit on climate litigation.

Do you have something to say about extreme weather events? We would love to hear your thoughts and feedback. What tactics have you used? What problems have you encountered? What have we missed? Please [get in touch](#).

About Social Change Lab

[Social Change Lab](#) conducts empirical research on disruptive protest and people-powered movements. Through research reports, workshops, and trainings, we provide actionable insights to help movements and funders be more effective. You can find all of our research projects and resources on [our website](#).